

THE METHODOLOGY OF USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING LISTENING COMPREHENSION IN ENGLISH CLASSES

Kurbonova Nilufar Azimboy qizi

A teacher of the secondary school № 21 in Termez city

Annotation

This article states the methodology of using innovative technologies in teaching listening comprehension in English classes and approaches of developing listening skills. The author emphasizes some criteria to develop listening skills and create some methods.

Key words: listening, method, strategy, approach, skill

Listening is a vital interpersonal communication skill. When we communicate we spend 45% of our time listening. Most people take listening for granted but it is not the same as hearing and should be thought of as a skill. Our listening skills page acts as an introduction to the subject and lists the ten principles of listening. Active listening provides a lot more information about how to listen effectively and can help we to avoid misunderstandings. We also have a page on Ineffective Listening, we may recognize some of the bad habits we or other people have picked up when listening. Reflection and clarification are both common techniques used to ensure that what we have heard and understood is what was intended -we can find out more on our pages Reflecting and Clarification.

Moreover, listening is the language modality that is used most frequently. It has been estimated that adults spend almost half their communication time listening, and pupils may receive as much as 90 % of their in-school information through listening to instructors and to one another. Often, however, language learners do not recognize the level of effort that goes into developing listening ability. Far from passively receiving and recording aural input, listeners actively involve themselves in the interpretation of what they hear, bringing their own background knowledge and linguistic knowledge to bear on the information contained in the aural text. Not all listening is the same; casual greetings, for example, require a different sort of listening capability than do academic lectures. Language learning requires intentional listening that employs strategies for identifying sounds and making meaning from them. Listening involves a sender (a person, radio, television), a message, and a receiver (the listener). Listeners often must process messages as they come, even if they are still processing what they have just heard, without backtracking or looking ahead.

In addition, listeners must cope with the sender's choice of vocabulary, structure, and rate of delivery. The complexity of the listening process is magnified in second

language contexts, where the receiver also has incomplete control of the language. Given the importance of listening in language learning and teaching, it is essential for language teachers to help their pupils become effective listeners. In the communicative approach to language teaching, this means modeling listening strategies and providing listening practice in authentic situations: those that learners are likely to encounter when they use the language outside the classroom. The one of the best ways introduce pupils to listening strategies is to integrate listening activities into language lessons using multimedia technology. As multimedia technology (interactive videodisc, CD-ROM, CD-I, etc.) becomes more accessible to teachers and learners of other languages, its potential as a tool to enhance listening skills becomes a practical option.

Multimedia allows integration of text, graphics, audio, and motion video in a range of combinations. The result is that learners can now interact with textual, aural, and visual media in a wide range of formats. The past two decades have brought to language teaching and learning a wide range of audio-visual technologies. From among these, no single tool for teaching and learning has had greater impact than the personal computer. Today, individual learners can, in addition to interacting with computer-generated text and graphics, control combinations of analog and digital sound and images. Arranging these combined media into intelligent, pedagogically-driven material is a challenge to teachers.

According to Howat and Macin, listening is the ability to identify and understand what others are saying. This involves understanding a speaker's accent or pronunciation, his grammar and his vocabulary, and grasping his meaning. An able listener is capable of doing these four things simultaneously. Willis lists a series of micro-skills of listening, which she calls enabling skills. They are:

- predicting what people are going to talk about
- guessing at unknown words or phrases without panicking
- using one's own knowledge of the subject to help one understand
- identifying relevant points; rejecting irrelevant information
- retaining relevant points (note-taking, summarizing)
- recognizing discourse markers, e.g., Well; Oh, another thing is; Now, finally; etc.
- recognizing cohesive devices, e.g., such as and which, including link words, pronouns, references, etc.
- understanding different intonation patterns and uses of stress, etc., which give clues to meaning and social setting
- understanding inferred information, e.g., speakers' attitude or intentions

The evidence that shows why listening is difficult comes mainly from four sources:

the message to be listened to, the speaker, the listener, and the physical setting.

The Message

Content. Many learners find it more difficult to listen to a taped message than to read the same message on a piece of paper, since the listening passage comes into the ear in the twinkling of an eye, whereas reading material can be read as long as the reader likes.

The listening material may deal with almost any area of life. It might include street gossip, proverbs, new products, and situations unfamiliar to the student. Also, in a spontaneous conversation speakers frequently change topics.

The content is usually not well organized.

In many cases listeners cannot predict what speakers are going to say, whether it is a news report on the radio, an interviewer's questions, an everyday conversation, etc. Messages on the radio or recorded on tape cannot be listened to at a slower speed. Even in conversation it is impossible to ask the speaker to repeat something as many times as the interlocutor might like.

Simple listening texts with little redundancy for lower-level students and complicated authentic materials with more redundancy for advanced learners. It has been reported that elementary-level students are not capable of interpreting extra information in the redundant messages, whereas advanced listeners may benefit from messages being expanded, paraphrased, etc.

Let's examine potential correspondence between multi modal processing opportunities for language learners in a multimedia environment and how these can interact to complement listening skills acquisition.

Retention of information in short term memory.

Most current multimedia Applications allow the student some control over the rate of language presentation. That is, users can start, stop, and review pieces of information to better understand and remember the aural text. The addition of video provides a clear, logical flow of events so that linking (remembering) new information to old is facilitated.

Discriminate the sounds of the target language.

User control over language presented in more than one modality supports a student's ability to discriminate where words begin and end. The synchronized display of text along with the aural text assists the learner in distinguishing phonetic groupings and boundaries. When learners can see the faces of those speaking in the video,

moreover, they can additionally make use of facial movements to understand the sound-meaning correspondence in the target language.

Recognize patterns of stress, rhythm, and intonation and how they signal information and intent.

Stress, rhythm, and intonation are automatically highlighted when aural language is divided into syntactic units. When we speak, the logical breaks in our discourse (the places where we pause ever so slightly) occur at syntactically predictable junctures. When specific words are stressed and patterns of intonation used, learners can be cued to closely examine the visual and spoken reactions of interlocutors in the video presentation.

Understand reduced speech.

Multimedia is particularly well suited to assist learners in their understanding of reduced forms of target language speech. Having the written version of fast, naturally-paced aural text on the computer screen allows the learner access to both the written and spoken forms simultaneously. That is, the learner may hear "wadjagonnado?" but will read "What are you going to do?" In this way, learners can come to understand the two different forms of the target language – spoken and written – as well as learn to decode these reduced forms.

Recognize core vocabulary and the rules and patterns of words used to communicate.

Coordinated aural, visual, and textual information on the computer screen at the same time makes up an ideal laboratory for student problem-solving at the level of individual words and sentence structures. The learner has at her disposal rich visual and contextual clues that can assist in breaking the code of the written and aural text. The multi modal cues can be cross-referenced for word, sentence-level and broader understanding.

Process different speech styles, different rates, and performance errors.

Rate and style of audio naturally vary according to the genre of the video selection. Many situation comedies, for example, exemplify slowed speech. Interlocutors speak slowly and deliberately so the joke can be processed and understood. There are other kinds of programming, talk shows, for example, that are very fast-paced and difficult for non-native speakers to comprehend. Multimedia that includes varied genres permits a broad experience of different voices with differing rates and speech styles. Pupils can control the aural text so they have sufficient time for their individual processing needs.

Recognize that meanings can be expressed in different grammatical forms.

Redundancy in video presentations is common. That is, interlocutors and narrators frequently repeat the same information in different ways so that meaning and intention is made clear to the viewer. In a multimedia format, phrases and sentences that carry the same or similar meaning can be highlighted for users and/or the learner can be prompted to highlight those phrases and sentences she feels express like meanings.

Infer meaning and make predictions using personal knowledge, experiences, and strategies.

Video is a medium to which language learners come well equipped. Pupils are very accustomed to inferring meaning and making predictions from what they see and hear on the screen. In a multimedia format, these viewing/comprehension strategies can be cued and guided by, for example, posing pre-viewing questions on top of the stilled first frame of the sequence they are about to watch. Inference, predication, and calling up prior knowledge and experience can thus be activated.

Apart from that, songs can be highly useful for developmental process of listening skills of a student.

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